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CONTEMPORARY ASPECTS OF THE USE OF ADHESIVE SYSTEMS IN THE FIXATION OF CERAMIC VENEERS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ADHESION STRENGTH, MICROLEAKAGE AND CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Annotation

Ceramic veneers are one of the most popular methods of aesthetic dental restoration in modern dentistry. The durability and clinical efficacy of veneers largely depend on the quality of the adhesive bond between the tooth tissue, the luting cement, and the internal surface of the restoration. The aim of this study was to compare modern adhesive systems and resin cements used for cementing ceramic veneers. A review of current literature on total-etch, self-etch, and universal adhesives, as well as various types of resin cements, was conducted. Adhesion strength, microleakage, marginal adaptation, and color stability were assessed. Total-etch systems were found to provide the highest bond strength to enamel and minimal microleakage, remaining the "gold standard" for veneer luting. Universal adhesives in selective-etch mode demonstrate comparable results with lower technical sensitivity. Light-cured resin cements demonstrated the best clinical performance among luting materials.

Keywords

Adhesive systems, ceramic veneers, resin cement, total-etch, self-etch, universal adhesives, microleakage, adhesion strength, aesthetic dentistry.

Introduction

Ceramic veneers are one of the most popular methods of restoring dental aesthetics in modern dentistry. Their high aesthetic properties, biocompatibility, and minimally invasive preparation have led to the widespread use of this technology in orthopedic practice. The longevity of veneers directly depends on the quality of the adhesive bond between the restoration and the underlying tooth tissue [1].

Various types of adhesive systems are currently used, differing in their mechanism of action, bond strength, microleakage, and technical sensitivity. Therefore, choosing the optimal adhesive protocol for veneer bonding remains a pressing issue in modern dentistry.

Purpose of the study

To conduct a comparative analysis of modern adhesive systems and fixing materials used in the installation of ceramic veneers, and to determine the most effective clinical fixation protocols.

Materials and methods of research

An analysis of current domestic and international literature on the use of total-etch, self-etch, and universal adhesive systems, as well as various types of resin cements in aesthetic dentistry, was conducted. Adhesion strength, microleakage, marginal adaptation, color stability, and restoration longevity were assessed (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of adhesive systems for fixing ceramic veneers

Adhesive system	Advantages	Flaws	Clinical features
Total-Etch (Etch-and-Rinse)	High adhesion strength to enamel; minimal microleakage; high durability	High technical sensitivity; risk of postoperative sensitivity; multi-stage	Recommended for enamel margins and complete

Adhesive system	Advantages	Flaws	Clinical features
			isolation of the working field
Self-Etch	Reduced postoperative sensitivity; ease of use; reduced risk of errors	Lower adhesion to enamel; possible increase in microleakage	Preferred for complex clinical conditions and work with dentin
Universal Adhesives	Versatility of application; selective-etch capability; presence of functional 10-MDP monomers	Efficiency differences between manufacturers; possible microleakage in self-etch mode	Allows you to customize the fixation protocol

A study by Alqurashi et al. (2025) compared the shear adhesion strength of four general-purpose adhesives [3]:

- *Optibond Universal* - 10.99 MPa (superficial dentin), 6.16 MPa (deep)
- Single Bond Universal - 9.72 MPa / 4.68 MPa
- Clearfil S3 Bond Universal - 9.38 MPa / 4.18 MPa
- G-Premio Universal Bond — 6.56 MPa / 2.41 MPa

Results and discussion.

Microleakage—the penetration of fluids and bacteria into the space between the veneer and tooth tissue—is a key indicator of durability. A study on models with 1,000 thermal cycles showed [2]:

- Etch-wash dual cure - minimal microleakage (0.90 at the neck, 0.60 at the cutting edge)
- Etch-wash light cure - moderate microleakage (1.70 / 1.00)
- Self-etch— increased micro-leakage
- Self-adhesive - maximum microleakage (3.00 / 1.60) [2]

Moreover, microleakage at the neck (dentin) is always higher than at the cutting edge (enamel), regardless of the system. This confirms that enamel is a more predictable tissue for adhesion [2].

Various authors point to self-adhesive cements' simplicity and time-saving benefits. However, research is unanimous: they are inferior to multi-step systems in terms of microleakage [2][5].

According to the curing mechanism, cements are divided into:

Light-cure (light-cured): better color stability, long working time, easy removal of excess before polymerization. Ideal for thin transparent veneers [6].

Dual-cure: a combination of light and chemical curing. Indicated for thick restorations where light does not fully penetrate. However, they are inferior to light-cure in terms of color stability [6].

Auto-cure (chemical): rarely used for veneers due to the risk of staining and difficulty of control [6].

According to adhesion technique. A comparative study of three main types of luting cements revealed significant differences in key clinical parameters [5]. The highest adhesion strength values were found for resin cement (24.8 MPa), significantly exceeding those of RMGIC (20.5 MPa) and zinc phosphate cement (18.9 MPa). A similar trend was observed for marginal adaptation, where resin cement demonstrated the best result (4.0), outperforming RMGIC (2.5) and zinc phosphate cement (3.2).

Micro-leakage indicators also confirmed the advantage of resin cement, which recorded minimal penetration (0.20 mm), while for RMGIC this indicator was 0.25 mm, and for zinc phosphate cement - 0.31 mm.

Thus, resin cement demonstrates the best results across all parameters studied, confirming its leading role in modern orthopedic dentistry for the cementation of ceramic restorations. Despite this, zinc phosphate cement, while inferior in functional characteristics, retains clinical significance primarily as a material for temporary restorations [5] (Table 2).

Pre-treatment of ceramics: HF vs. sandblasting.

For glass ceramics (lithium disilicate, feldspar ceramics), the "gold standard" remains hydrofluoric acid etching (HF 5–9.8%) + silanization [4]. HF selectively dissolves the glass phase, creating micropores 5–10 µm deep [4].

HF does not work for zirconium, as the material is resistant to acids. Here, air-particle abrasion (Al_2O_3 50 µm) and an MDP-containing primer are used [4][7]. HF creates micropores in the glass phase; silane binds SiO_2 to the cement [4]. HF does not affect the crystalline structure; MDP binds to ZrO_2 [4][7]. Some authors propose alternative methods (laser treatment, heated HF etching), but clinical data are still limited [4].

Table 2. Comparative recommendations for the selection of materials

Situation	The best choice	Alternative	Reason for choice
Veneers on enamel, experienced doctor	Total-etch + light-cure cement	Selective-etch universal	Maximum strength and tightness
Veneers with dentin extension	Universal selective-etch	Self-etch	A compromise between strength and simplicity
Zirconium veneers	Air-abrasion + MDP-primer + dual-cure	—	The characteristics of the material require a different protocol.
Limited experience / difficult isolation	Self-adhesive resin cement	Self-etch	Minimum steps, less risk of error
Maximum aesthetics	Light-cure resin cement	—	Better color stability

The conducted analysis allows us to formulate the following conclusions:

By adhesive systems. Total-etch remains the "gold standard" for enamel margins due to its maximum strength and minimal microleakage [1][2]. Self-etch offers a compromise between simplicity and quality, but is inferior in strength to enamel [1]. Universal adhesives provide flexibility, but their effectiveness in self-etch mode on enamel is lower than that of classical systems [3]. Selective-etch mode allows universal adhesives to achieve results comparable to total-etch [2].

On cements. Resin cements outperform RMGIC and zinc phosphate in all key parameters [5]. Light-cure systems are preferred for veneers due to their color stability and ease of excess removal [6]. Self-adhesive cements simplify the protocol but reduce adhesion strength and increase microleakage [2][5].

On pre-treatment of ceramics: for glass ceramics, the combination of HF + silane is irreplaceable; for zirconium, air-particle abrasion + MDP [4]. Incorrect choice of method (for example, HF for zirconium) leads to a sharp drop in adhesion strength [4].

Conclusion

The analysis showed that total-etch systems retain their status as the "gold standard" for bonding ceramic veneers due to their high adhesion strength and minimal microleakage. Universal adhesives in selective-etch mode provide comparable clinical results with lower technical sensitivity. Light-curing resin cements demonstrated superior color stability and marginal adaptation. The choice of adhesive system should be individualized, taking into account the type of ceramic, preparation depth, and clinical isolation conditions.

References

1. Alara Dental. Dental Adhesive Systems Guide 2026 for Modern Practices [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://alaradental.com/blog/dental-adhesive-systems>
2. Haralur SB. Microleakage of porcelain laminate veneers cemented with different bonding techniques // J Clin Exp Dent. — 2018. — Vol. 10, No. 2. - P. e166–e171. - PMC5899795.

3. Alqurashi H. et al. Evaluation of Four Different Adhesive Systems' Bonding Strength Between Superficial and Deep Dentin // *Materials*. — 2025. — Vol. 18, No. 13. - P. 3107. - DOI: 10.3390/ma18133107
4. Bonding Protocols for Lithium Disilicate Veneers // *PMC*. - 2024. - PMC11940404.
5. A Comparative Evaluation of the Bonding Strength, Marginal Adaptation, and Microleakage of Dental Cements in Prosthodontics // *PMC*. - 2024. - PMC11346805.
6. Current Protocols for Resin-Bonded Dental Ceramics [PDF]. — Access mode: <https://www.perioimplantchicago.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/current-protocols-for-resin-bonded-dental-ceramics.pdf>
7. Anh N.V. et al. Shear bond strength of MDP-containing light-cured veneer adhesive system to zirconia with different surface preparations // *J Adhes Sci Technol*. — 2024. — Vol. 38. - P. 2336–2349. — DOI: 10.1080/01694243.2023.2293382
8. Self-Etching Bonding vs. Total Etch Bonding 2026 Guide [Electronic resource]. — Alara Dental. — Access mode: <https://alaradental.com/blog/self-etching-bonding-vs-total-etch-bonding>
9. Peumans M. et al. Porcelain veneers: A review of the literature // *J Dent*. - 2000. - Vol. 28. - P. 163–177. — DOI: 10.1016/S0300-5712(99)00066-4
10. Expert tips and tricks for veneer cementation [Electronic resource]. — Solventum Dental Blog. — 2025. — Access mode: <https://dentalblog.solventum.com/expert-tips-and-tricks-for-veneer-cementation/>